

Indentation models and failure mode map for circular composite sandwich plates

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ABSTRACT:

Competing failure modes are investigated for circular sandwich plates comprising quasi-isotropic (QI) E-glass/epoxy composite faceplates (with $[-60/0/60]_{ns}$ configuration) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) foam core under bending. Clamped sandwich plates are loaded using flat-ended punch at the center of the plate. Three competing failure modes, viz., core indentation, core shear and face failure/microbuckling, are considered. Analytical estimates for elastic response (stiffness) and initial failure load are proposed, and these are verified by experimental measurements and finite element (FE) simulated tests from LS-DYNA solver.

During post-indentation-failure behavior (load-displacement response), the faceplate undergoes stretching. Hence large deformation behavior of the faceplate is essential to consider in the analytical formulation. Hence, axisymmetric response of a circular composite sandwich plate subjected to indentation by a rigid flat punch is examined. Flat punch is assumed to impose an axisymmetric line load. Small deformation response is investigated by solving the equilibrium equations exactly, while large deformation response is estimated using Berger's method. The indentation behavior is predicted numerically by modeling core as a (i) continuum foam and (ii) plate on foundation with reaction force (i.e. interaction problem) by employing user interaction subroutine in commercial finite element package ABAQUS.

Derived analytical estimates for the indentation loads, failure modes and post-indentation behavior are in agreement with finite element predictions and experimental measurements.

Keywords: circular sandwich plates, bending, indentation, core shear, facesheet micro-buckling, failure mode map

1. INTRODUCTION:

Sandwich structures have superior specific strength and stiffness compared to monolithic plates made from either core or faceplate materials. However, due to relatively low stiffness and strength of the core, sandwich structures are susceptible to localized core indentation damage due to tool drops, bird and hail impact. Stress and failure analysis of sandwich structures under quasi-static localized loads and low velocity impact using experimental tests can be expensive while finite element (FE) predictions are computationally intensive. Hence, there is a need for analytical modeling of the deformation and failure behavior of composite sandwich plates for design purpose.

A collection of literature on the design of sandwich beams with discussion on competing failure modes and corresponding failure mode maps is given by [1, 2]. Most of the literature deals with sandwich beams consisting of metallic faceplates. However, with the increase in the use of

composites for light weight sandwich construction, it is necessary to construct the failure mode maps for composite sandwich structures. Very few publications have emphasized on the failure mode maps for composite sandwich structures. In specific, most of the literature is relevant to sandwich beams with no contributions on plate studies. Literature on composite sandwich beams are: cross-ply GFRP/honeycomb [3] and plane weave GFRP/PVC foam [4-6]. Effect of beam support conditions (viz., simply support or clamp) on the failure mode map of sandwich beams is investigated by Tagarielli et al. [7].

After the indentation failure, faceplate experiences stretching from large deformation while core exerts elastic-plastic reaction force onto the faceplate. In literature, large deformation behavior under spherical punch is addressed by several authors using variety of approximate methods. During the analysis, the core is assumed to exert either rigid-perfectly-plastic (RPP) or elastic-perfectly-plastic (EPP) response for the sake of analytical easiness. Türk and Hoo-Fatt [8] derived assumed bending rigidity, D_f and in-plane displacements $u;v$ of the faceplate were considered to have negligible effect on the indentation behavior. Hosseini et al. [9] extended Türk and Hoo-Fatt [8] formulation to arbitrary layup laminates with rectangular plates.

To the best of authors' knowledge, no reported results on the failure mode maps are available in the literature for composite sandwich plates. In the present work, failure mode map for clamped circular composite sandwich plate is constructed. Sandwich plates are manufactured from E-quasi-isotropic GFRP/PVC foam core. E-glass epoxy prepregs are laid in $[-60/0/60]_{ns}$ configuration. To predict this post-indentation behavior, analytical equations were derived. Small deformation solution is derived by solving the equilibrium differential equation. However, large deformation solution is derived by considering Berger's approximation [10]. Existing formulations [8] are in-principle spherical punch formulations rather than flat punch.

2. SANDWICH PLATE FAILURE MODE MAP

In this section, analytical formulae for the elastic stiffness and failure initiation load of a clamped circular sandwich plate are presented.

Consider a clamped circular sandwich plate with symmetric faceplates perfectly bonded to foam core, which is loaded by a rigid circular flat-ended punch at the center of the plate as shown in Fig. 1. Let R be the plate radius, a the punch radius, c the core thickness and t the faceplate thickness. Young's and shear moduli of core are E_c and G_c , respectively; σ_c and τ_c are the strengths of the core material in uniaxial compression and shear loading conditions, respectively. The faceplates of the sandwich have Young's modulus E_f , Poisson's ratio ν_f and strength σ_f . Let P be the centrally applied load and δ the corresponding displacement of the punch during the bending of sandwich plate. For mathematical analysis, following non-dimensional geometrical (viz., \bar{c} , \bar{t} , \bar{R}), and material parameters (viz., \bar{E} ; \bar{G} ; $\bar{\rho}$; $\bar{\tau}$; $\bar{\sigma}$) are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{c} &= \frac{c}{R}, & \bar{t} &= \frac{t}{c}, & \bar{R} &= \frac{R}{a}, & \bar{\sigma} &= \frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_f} \\ \bar{\tau} &= \frac{\tau_c}{\sigma_f}, & \bar{E} &= \frac{E_c}{E_f}, & \bar{G} &= \frac{E_c}{G_f}, & \bar{\rho} &= \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_f} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Of all the variables in Eq. (1) only \bar{c} and \bar{t} are considered to be free variables while others are kept constant for constructing the failure mode map. Through out the analysis, quasi-isotropic layup is considered for the faceplate. Failure mode map is constructed for sandwich plate with Divinycell H35 polyvinyl chloride (PVC) foam core. To investigate the post-indentation-failure response, H35, H45, H80 and H100 foam cored sandwich plates were used. Experimentally measured material properties of the foams and faceplate material are given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1: Properties of foam materials

Property	H35	H45	H80	H100
Density (kg/m ³): ρ_c	38	45	80	100
Compression modulus (MPa): E_c	22	35	49	52
Compression strength (MPa): σ_c	0.5	0.7	1.2	2
Shear strength (MPa): τ_c	0.3	-	-	-

Table 2: Properties of faceplate materials

UD-GFRP		QI-GFRP	
Density (kg/m ³)	2200	Density (kg/m ³): ρ_f	2200
Tensile modulus (GPa): E_{11}, E_{22}	46, 13	Tensile modulus (GPa): E_{xx}, E_{yy}, E_{zz}	25.3, 25.3, 13
Tensile strength (MPa): X_t, Y_t	1330, 50	Tensile strength(MPa): X_t, Y_t	407, 240
Compression strength (MPa): X_c, Y_c	537, 130	Compression strength(MPa): X_c, Y_c	275, 250
Shear modulus (GPa): G_{12}, G_{31}, G_{23}	7, 6.5, 4.48	Shear modulus (GPa): G_{xy}, G_{yz}	10, 5.46
Shear strength (MPa): τ_{12}, τ_{21}	65, 40	Shear strength (MPa): τ_{xy}	76
Poisson's ratio: $\nu_{12}, \nu_{31}, \nu_{23}$	0.25, 0.074, 0.44	Poisson's ratio: ν_{yx}, ν_{zx}	0.24, 0.175

Expressions sandwich plate stiffness is derived using the classical plate theory, Mindlin's plate theory and Reddy's third order plate theory. Simplistic design equations are derived for core indentation, core shear and faceplate failure. All the variables are non-dimensionalized and the failure mode map is constructed as shown in Figure 1. Using the failure mode map, optimizing the sandwich structures for a given load index becomes easy. This methodology can be used for any arbitrary circular sandwich plates.

Figure 1: Failure mode map for sandwich plate with PVC foam core (H35) and glass/epoxy laminate (with quasi-isotropic lay-up). This is plotted for non-dimensional variables $\bar{R} = 8$, $\bar{\sigma} = 0.0021$, $\bar{\tau} = 0.00125$, $\bar{E} = 0.00087$ and $\bar{G} = 0.004$.

3. POST-INDENTATION RESPONSE

To investigate the post indentation response of the sandwich plate, core is assumed to be RPP foundation and two solutions were derived by considering (a) small deformation and (b) large deformations of the faceplate. Small deformation solution is derived by solving the equilibrium equations in exact manner. However, considering large deformations of the faceplate gives two simultaneous coupled differential equations and hence solved using Berger's approximate method [10]. Typical post-indentation load displacement curves from are shown in Figure 2. In the small deformation they it is possible to consider the EPP behavior of the foam. However, in the large deformation analysis, foam is assumed to have RPP behavior due to the geometric nonlinear analysis. Effect of faceplate thickness, t is investigated using 0.7 mm and 1.3 mm faceplates. Small deformation solution starts to deviate from the experimental/finite element solutions for $\delta/t > 1.5$.

Figure 3 Indentation load versus non-dimensional displacement responses for sandwich plates under FP loading. Hosseini curves are plotted from Hosseini et al [9].

4. CONCLUSIONS

Bending response of clamped circular composite sandwich plate with E-glass/epoxy faceplates and PVC foam core has been studied. Later, analytical formulations to estimate the post-indentation failure response of the composite sandwich plates subjected to quasi-static indentation by a rigid flat punch.

- Stiffness estimates from classical plate theory, Mindlin's theory are deviating from the experimental/FE predictions. Hence, semi-analytical method is proposed (based on equivalent single layer third order plate theory) to estimate the stiffness of the sandwich plate.
- Core indentation dominated designs with thin face and thin core can be better modeled using higher order sandwich plate theories as these geometries undergo overall global deflection before it undergoes core indentation failure.
- Berger's approximate differential equations are considered for RPP foundation and the differential equations are solved exactly for flat punch loading.

The failure mode map for circular composite sandwich plates is first of its kind in the literature.

Acknowledgement

A. Rajaneesh thanks Nanyang Technological University (NTU), Singapore for the financial support in the form of a graduate student assistantship.

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